

Large area uniform 1-dimensional TiO₂ nano-forest as photoanodes for efficient and stable perovskite solar cells fabrication

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Abstract

During the last years, perovskite solar cells have gained intriguing interest among the photovoltaic community, in particular after reaching performances at par with mature thin film based PV. This rapid evolution has been fostered by the finding of new perovskite stoichiometries and device architectures. In the present work, we report the fabrication of perovskite solar cells based on highly ordered 1-dimensional vertically oriented TiO₂ nano-forests, which are uniform on large area. These vertically oriented porous TiO₂ photoanodes were deposited by physical vapour deposition in an oblique angle configuration, a method which is scalable to fabricate large area devices. Mixed or triple cation based perovskites were then infiltrated into these 1-dimensional nano structures and power conversion efficiencies c.a. 17% along with improved stability were obtained. The fabricated devices were found to be more stable when compare to the classical 3-dimensional TiO₂ deposited by wet chemistry. These 1-D photoanode will be of interest for scale up of technology, in other opto-electrical devices as they can be easily fabricated utilizing industrially adapted.

Key words: Solar cells; perovskite solar cells; 1-Directional structures; Photoanode; Charge transfer

1. Introduction

Currently, the field of Photovoltaics (PV) is dominated by silicon PV technology. Among possible alternatives are thin-film based technologies and molecular solar cells. In recent years hybrid inorganic-organic perovskite based solar cells have positioned itself very well within this context and are now at par with mature thin film based CIGS $\{\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})(\text{Se,S})_2\}$ technology in terms of efficiencies¹⁻⁶. A light to electricity conversion efficiency in excess of 22% is reported for this emerging cells, and high expectations arisen with respect to a near future transfer and adaptation of laboratory based processes to a pre-commercial stage. In perovskite solar cells, the active materials act as light absorber has an ABX_3 type perovskite structure. The use of perovskite has transformed through time and from MAPbI_3 to compositional engineered, mixed perovskites are being employed for the fabrication of highly efficient solar cells^{7,8}.

The charges are highly mobile in perovskite and the conduction and the valence band energy levels are well suited for applications in solar energy^{4,7}. The perovskite layer is sandwiched between two charge selective contacts which generate the driving force for the charge separation. Upon illumination of light, electrons are transferred to the conduction band of an electron-transport layer while the holes are transferred to a hole-transport material (HTM)⁷. Commercially available anatase TiO_2 colloidal particles are the most exploited metal oxide used as electron transporting material^{1,3} (ETM). The thickness of the electron transport materials and its interfaces are key parameters for the fabrication of efficient and stable solar cells. The electron selective contact not only transports the electronic charges but also influences growth of perovskite crystal formation. The use of one-dimensional metal oxides (e.g. TiO_2 , ZnO) structures can be an attractive strategy to allow uni-directional and fast charge collection, higher absorption of active materials and light management due to scattering within 1-dimension structures. In the past, TiO_2 based nano-tubes were a subject to intense investigation in sensing and other electro-optical application⁹⁻¹⁴.

1-D based structures, allows to fabricate large surface-to-volume ratio, uni-dimensionality along with high surface reactivity and widely used in electro-catalysis, photo-catalysis, sensing and for other energy storage application. Anodization¹² of metal plate remains to be an approach to produce 1-D structures, however they need to be transferred on a foreign substrate and contains defects, uniformity over a large area and uniform pore size control remains a tricky aspects, and thus limited to lab curiosity. Using template method and wet chemistry approach, it is also possible to produce 1-D structures, however large area, uniformity and batch to batch reproducibility of 1-D structures was difficult to achieve¹³.

In the commonly studied mesoscopic perovskite solar cells, a mesoporous structure is coated atop of a blocking layer. Some reports suggest this as nucleating site for perovskite growth, which allow fabricating continuous perovskite layers, and thus influencing the charge selective properties of the ETM. However, the existence of grain boundaries between the nano-particles of the porous layer increases the trapping sites and the electron recombination rate. One-dimensional (1D) TiO₂ nanostructures (nano-wires, nano-tubes or nano-rods) was earlier found to have lower charge recombination rate at the grain boundaries and a facile electron injection pathway due to the unidirectional along the axis charge transport in a dye sensitized solar cells (DSSCs). The enhanced performance in 1D-TiO₂ perovskite solar cells was possibly due to the higher light harvesting abilities and lower recombination losses with respect to 3D-TiO₂ as measured by impedance spectroscopy¹⁴.

The versatility to deposit perovskite using wet chemistry^{4,7} vapor deposition or in a mix process utilizing a solution process for the inorganic precursor and vapor assisted for the organic component¹ makes it attractive for the manufacturing of a large variety of cell architectures.

The use of 1-D nanostructures (nano-columns, nano-rods, nano-wires) was reported to be effective in enhancing electron transport properties for different solar cells including silicon¹⁵, III-V semiconductors¹⁶, organic photovoltaics¹⁷ and DSSCs¹⁸⁻²⁰. Additionally, the use these 1-D nanostructures will not only benefit the transport properties along the axis but, contributing to

minimize the reflection of light due to their generally low-refractive index, they favor the absorption of light by the active components enhancing the light harvesting efficiency. In DSSCs the use of 1-D nanostructures was found to have a positive effect in increasing the amount of dye absorption, improve transport properties and carriers lifetime, thus giving rise to photocurrents comparable with those of equivalent mesoporous nano-particle cells^{21,22}. Based on these ideas, in the present work we have prepared porous photoanodes based on vertically aligned 1D-TiO₂ thin films prepared by the physical vapor deposition method at oblique incidences angles (PVD-OAD)²³⁻²⁵ and used them for the fabrication of perovskite solar cells in a similar fashion. To further improve the cell performance, herein we have optimized mixed {Formamidinium (FA), methylammonium (MA)} and triple cation (FA/MA/Cs) based perovskites, tuning of the thickness of the photoanode to influence of morphological parameters such as porosity, of the 1-D TiO₂, with an aim to increase photovoltaic performance magnitudes such as short circuit current (J_{SC}), open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}), fill factor (FF) and thus PCE.

It is worth noting regarding the future scaling up of the technology that uniform 1-directional nano-forest photoanodes can be easily prepared over larger areas using this PVD technique²⁵. Earlier nanostructured²⁶⁻²⁸ based photoanodes (thickness 500-1500nm) was utilized for perovskite solar cells fabrication, while thinner photoanode of nano-structured TiO₂ were also found by us to be rather effective for device fabrication^{23,24}. It is expected that nano-forest based photoanodes showed even better light harvesting efficiencies by enhancing the light scattering properties of the devices. As a consequence of the effective transport of charge along the nano-forest an increase in PCE could be obtained. To the best of our understanding this is the best result so far reported for any 1D-nanostructured photoanodes in perovskite solar cells. Large area uniform 1D structures as ETM in perovskite solar cells has also not been reported so far. Combined with the benefits of light-scattering centers and low ionic diffusion resistance, the performance of solar cell was improved to a great extent. These successful attempts to simplify the manufacturing operation of

charge selective contacts will be an encouraging step for the large-scale implementations in plethora of other opto-electrical devices.

2. Experimental

Materials

All chemicals were commercial products either from Sigma Aldrich or Agros and were employed without any treatment or purification. 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(*N,N*-di-*p*-methoxyphenylamine)-9,9-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) was acquired from Merck KGaA. Methylamine iodide, CH₃NH₃I (MAI, FAI, MABr were bought from Dyesol and PbI₂ and PbBr₂ were bought from TCI. While chlorobenzene, anhydrous DMF, DMSO and CsI were procured from Sigma–Aldrich.

Preparation of TiO₂ nano-forest Photoanode

1-Dimensional nanostructured TiO₂ thin films depicting as nano-forest were used as an electron transport photoanodes. They consisted of a porous structured layer made of vertically aligned nano-columns with an approximate thickness of either 100 or 200nm. These TiO₂ porous photoanodes were prepared at room temperature by physical vapor deposition at oblique incidence (PVD-OAD) in an electron beam evaporator using a modified procedure with respect to previous publications²¹⁻²⁵. Basically, the method implies placing the substrate surface at a glancing angle with respect to the evaporation source. Operational conditions such as beam current, oxygen partial pressure during deposition or distance from the target are kept similar than those reported in these previous works. In the present experiment the zenithal evaporation angle (α) defined between the normal to the substrate and the flux of evaporation material was fixed at 80°. In a fix configuration, varying the mentioned zenithal angle can be used to tailor the tilting angle of the nano-columns, as well as the porosity and other properties of the films²⁵. In the present investigation, to obtain vertical nanostructured with increase porosity of the layer we have azimuthally turned the substrate during deposition (40 rpm) and controlled the deposition time to obtained two different nanostructure thickness, i.e., 100 or 200 nm.

Device fabrication

TEC glasses ($15\Omega/\text{sq}$) was used as substrate and was cleaned by ultrasonication in 2% Hellmanex water solution for 30 minutes followed by rinsing with deionized water and ethanol. Then, $\sim 40\text{nm}$ TiO_2 compact layer was deposited on FTO substrate via spray pyrolysis at $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ from a precursor solution of titanium diisopropoxidebis-(acetylacetonate) in anhydrous ethanol. After the spraying, the substrates were left at $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 45 minutes and allowed to cool down till room temperature. These substrates were then used for the deposition of the TiO_2 nano-forest photoanodes by PV-OAD and, for comparative purposes, a standard mesoporous layer of TiO_2 deposited using the spin coating for 30 s at 4000 rpm was used. As starting material, we used a TiO_2 paste (Dyesol 30 NR-D) diluted in ethanol (1:7) to achieve 150–200 nm thick layer. After the deposition of the TiO_2 photoanodes, either by spin coating or PV-OAD, the samples were dried at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min and then annealed again at $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min under dry air flow. This thermal treatment aims at transforming the otherwise amorphous TiO_2 layers into anatase. After cooling down to $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the substrates with the TiO_2 photoanodes were transferred to an atmospheric glovebox for depositing the perovskite films. The perovskite films were deposited from a precursor solution containing FAI (1 M), PbI_2 (1.2 M), MABr (0.2 M), and PbBr_2 (0.2 M) in anhydrous DMF:DMSO 4:1 (v:v). The perovskite solution was spin coated in a two-step program at 1000 and 4000 rpm for 10 and 30 s, respectively. During the second step, $100\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of chlorobenzene was used as an antisolvent and poured on the substrate 15 s prior the end of the program. The substrates were then annealed at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h in a glovebox. For the triple cation based perovskite (CsFAMA), CsI was separately dissolved (1.5 M stock solution in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)), and added to the mixed perovskite precursor to achieve the 5% composition. Followed by the perovskite annealing and cooling, the hole transport layer was deposited using Spiro-OMeTAD (70 mM in chlorobenzene) was spun coated at 4000 rpm for 20s. Spiro-

OMeTAD was doped with bis-(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide lithium salt (Li-TFSI, from Aldrich), tris(2-(1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-4-tert-butylpyridine)cobalt(III)-tris(bis-(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide) (FK209, from Dynamo), and 4-tert-Butylpyridine (*t-BP*, from Aldrich). The molar ratio of additives for HTMs was: 0.5, 0.03, and 3.3 for Li-TFSI, FK209, and *t-BP*, respectively. To finish the devices, 70–80 nm of gold was thermally evaporated under low vacuum ($10^{-5} \times 10^{-6}$) as cathode. All solutions were prepared inside an argon glove box with controlled moisture and oxygen conditions.

Characterization

Current density–voltage (*J–V*) curves were recorded with a Keithley 2400 source-measurement-unit under AM 1.5 G, 100 mW cm² illumination from a certified Class AAA, 450 W solar simulator (ORIEL, 94023 A). Light output power was calibrated using a NREL certified calibrated mono-crystalline silicon solar cell. A black metal mask (0.16 cm²) was placed over the square shaped device (active area 0.5 cm²) to reduce the influence of scattered light. The scan rate 10mV/sec was used for measuring the devices and optimized as such to calculate the accurate value for efficiencies without having hysteresis effect. For IPCE 150 W xenon lamp coupled to an Oriel Cornerstone 260 motorized ¼ m monochromator as the light source, and a 2936-R power meter to measure the short circuit current was used. The cross-sectional microscopy image as well as topography was captured using a Hitachi S5200 field-emission microscope operating at 5.0 keV.

The Transmittance and reflectance spectra of the TiO₂ nano-forests on FTO before and after perovskite deposition were measured using Perkin Elmer, UV-vis-NIR lambda 1050 spectrophotometer equipped with 160 mm integrating sphere. Refractive index and thickness of the nano-structured TiO₂ thin films was calculated by fitting their transmittance spectra using home-made code software based on the well-known transfer-matrix procedure³⁰. The code considered a typical Cauchy dispersion for the wavelength dependence of the refractive index of

the films. The reported thicknesses of the porous layers obtained as an output of the fitting procedure is in agreement with the values determined experimentally by the SEM micrographs analysis.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of TiO₂ nano-forest based perovskite solar cells.

3. Results and discussion

A schematic configuration of the fabricated perovskite solar cells is shown in Fig. 1, it represents the scheme of a device incorporating a nano-forest TiO₂ acting as photoanode in the perovskite solar cell.

The optical properties and microstructure of the TiO₂ photoanode layers was elucidated by UV-vis transmission spectroscopy and SEM analysis, respectively. Figure 2a shows experimental and simulated UV-vis transmission spectra, both of them running in similar accord. The simulation analysis rendered thickness values of these two layers of 109 and 216 nm and a refraction index of 1.74 for the samples and an estimated porosity in the order of 60% of the total volume of the film (rough calculation by taking into account that compact TiO₂ thin films have a refraction index of around 2.4 and that the pores are filled with air during the analysis).

Figure 2b shows the transmittance (T) and reflectance (R) measured by integrating sphere before and after deposition of perovskite over FTO glass covered by thin compact layer of TiO₂ and absorbance was calculated by subtracting reflectance and transmittance using the equation $1-R-T$.

In both 100 and 200 nm TiO₂ nano-forest based photoanode, the absorbance (A) maxima was at 500-550 nm due to high extinction coefficient of perovskite in this region and in rest spectral region from 400-750nm, absorbance reaches up to 80 % and 70% in case of 100 and 200 nm thick nano-forest photoanode (Fig. 2b). However, the highest absorbance up to 90 % was found for 200 nm nano-forest due to larger grains and porosity, thus more perovskite was infiltrated inside the pores and on the surface as well.

Fig. 3a-d shows a series of cross section micrographs for the nano-forest TiO₂ as well as for the devices. Fig.3a and 3c show cross section of the nano-forest TiO₂ layers of 100nm and 200nm respectively grown on a silicon substrate. The micrographs show that the films microstructure consists of vertically oriented uniform 1-dimensional nanostructured defining a forest-like structure. Comparing the two films, it is also apparent that the photoanode made up of 200 nm thick TiO₂ film have thickened as they have grown in length. This columnar thickening effect is typical of OAD films²⁵ and gives rise to a surface topography (c.f. normal SEM micrographs in Fig 3e-3f) consisting of bigger grains and larger pore entrances at the surface. Moreover, these two normal images of nano-forest TiO₂ layers reveal that the individual nano-columnar structures are extremely well ordered and homogeneously distributed over the substrate. Similar microstructures are difficult to achieve with TiO₂ thin films deposited by wet chemistry routes, which generally possess an uneven dispersion and considerable aggregation of nano-particles and a poor interfacial contact between the layers material and the substrate. Some undesirable consequences of these microstructures in solar cells are poor electron transfer and high charge recombination rate, both contributing to decrease their overall efficiency.

Fig. 3b and 3d, depicts that in addition of perovskite infiltration into these TiO₂ structures, a thick conformal capping layer of perovskites formed atop of it.

Figure 2. a) Experimental and simulated transmission spectra for different thickness of TiO_2 nano-forest grown on quartz, b) calculated absorbance ($A=1-R-T$) from measured transmittance (T) and reflectance(R) spectra by integrating sphere for different thickness of TiO_2 nano-forest grown on FTO before and after incorporation of the perovskite film, b) 100 nm thick TiO_2 nano-forest film, c) the 200 nm thick TiO_2 nano-forest film, d) and e) after deposition of perovskite.

Figure 3. a) Cross section scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of TiO₂ nano-forest films of 100 nm thick grown on Si substrate, b) cross section of device with 100nm TiO₂ nano-forest, c) cross section image of the 200 nm thick TiO₂ nano-forest on silicon substrate, d) cross section of device with 200nm TiO₂ nano-forest e) top view image of the 100 nm thick TiO₂ nano-forest and f) top view image of a 200 nm thick TiO₂ nano-forest.

A very intimate and sharp interface can be seen from the cross sectional image of fabricated solar cells. From bottom to top of this image, layers due to FTO (400 nm), compact TiO₂ (ca. 50-60 nm), TiO₂ nano-forest (ca. 100 or 200nm) and perovskite (ca.400 nm) are clearly distinguished. Atop of perovskite capping layer the hole transporting material (Spiro-OMeTAD) 150nm and the metallic cathode as gold layer (c.a. 80nm) can be easily distinguished. The device cross sectional image is in well agreement with the architect (Fig. 1), and the layers are stacked accordingly without any defects or large inhomogeneity. It is important to note that large area uniform 1-D porous structures were fabricated with the implementation of the PV-OAD technique.

Earlier, with the help of ToF-SIMS, we proved a homogeneous infiltration of the perovskite in the pores of the TiO₂ 1D-nanostructured TiO₂ films prepared by PV-OAD without azimuthal rotation and a thickness higher than >500nm. Considering the 100-200 nm thickness of the photoanode with vertical orientation utilized in the present work, we can reasonably assume that the perovskite has effectively filled the inter-columnar space in the films studied in the present work.

The device photovoltaic parameters are summarized in the Table 1 and the *J-V* curves are shown in Fig. 4. We have observed that the devices based on nano-forest based structure performed better than the devices fabricated from 3-dimensional TiO₂ deposited through wet chemistry techniques (spin coating of diluted TiO₂ paste). Increments in V_{OC} and in J_{SC} were observed when compare to 3-dimensional TiO₂ structures. More importantly the FF of the devices increases significantly, and for 200nm thick TiO₂ nano-forest it was 74.5%, which is highly competitive for perovskite solar cells. This increase in FF pointing towards the low recombination in these devices. No significant difference was found between 100 or 200 nm thick TiO₂ nano-forest.

100nm thick gave slightly higher V_{oc} (1077mV) compare to 200 nm (1046 mV), due to low series resistance. In the past, using TiO_2 nano-columnar structures prepared by PV-OAD without rotation, best PV properties were obtained from 200nm thick layers, which yielded a PCE of 10.53% with $MAPbI_3$ based perovskites. We speculate for a thicker TiO_2 nano-forest layers, the thickness of perovskite layer (infiltration + capping layer) is higher, higher efficiency in photon collection and conversion into electrons, can be obtained. Fig. 5 shows the IPCE spectra of the perovskite solar cells, and a very flat IPCE spectrum is obtained in the 400-700nm region, the IPCE is close to 80% in these cells. The integrated current is in well agreement with the $J-V$ curves and is represented on secondary Y-axis of Fig.4 Similar profile was shown by 200nm-thick nano-forest as well as

Figure 4. Current-voltage curve for different photoanode based perovskite solar cells at 1 sun conditions. mesoporous TiO_2 , while 100nm thick nano-forest shows slightly lower photo-to-electron conversion. 200nm thick TiO_2 nano-forest based photoanodes showed improved current as well as V_{oc} were the best in terms of current but 200nm thick ones showed a significantly better voltage performance and a higher FF and as a result, gave the best PCE of 16.8%. Notably, the PCE of nano-forest based devices supersede the mesoporous based PSCs. The main difference can be seen from the increase in the value of FF values originated from lower recombination from ETM.

Table 1. Performance of the perovskite sensitized solar cells fabricated employing vertical TiO₂ nano-columns as photoanodes.

Thickness ^a (nm)	Perovskites	J_{SC} (mA cm ⁻²)	V_{OC} (mV)	FF	PCE (%)
100	FAPbI ₃ (0.85)MAPbBr ₃ (0.15) + Cs _{0.5}	20.78	1077	72.18	16.17
200	FAPbI ₃ (0.85)MAPbBr ₃ (0.15) + Cs _{0.5}	21.24	1061	74.53	16.80
1:7 TiO ₂	FAPbI ₃ (0.85)MAPbBr ₃ (0.15) + Cs _{0.5}	20.68	1046	68.68	14.86

^aThickness of the PVD-OAD TiO₂ nanocolumns based photoanode.

The light irradiation has to travel through ETM, thus based on the thickness and transmittance, the IPCE profiles exhibit different intensities particularly at the wavelengths where ETM shows absorbance. The IPCE profiles show significant improvements between 350-650 nm with a peak value of 83.2% at 514 nm and between 350 to 500 nm with a peak value around 79.2% at 366 nm for PSCs based on nano-forest and mesoporous, respectively. The obtained improvements in IPCE values at specific wavelengths are due to the lower trap sites or recombination.

Though we expect facile charge injection between photoanode and perovskite layers, there is no clue that the excitons generated in the HTMs layer are dissociated into photocurrent in the comparison between the IPCE profiles and the absorption spectra in Figure 2a. We can speculate that nano-forest photoanode play the roles of extraction and transportation of charge carriers.

Figure 5. IPCE curves for the solar cells with different thickness of TiO₂.

Figure 6. Evolution of the photovoltaic parameters (PCE, J_{SC} , V_{OC} and FF) for nano-forest TiO₂ photoanodes and standard mp-TiO₂ ones at 1 sun condition.

Fig. 6 represents, the PV parameters plotted as a function of time to observe the stability of the PSCs fabricated using TiO₂ nano-forest as well as standard mesoporous structure. The un-encapsulated devices were subject to periodically J - V measurements and for this the devices were kept under dark conditions under ambient atmosphere (<55-60% R.H.). Significant improvement in the stability was observed in the case of 1-D vertically oriented TiO₂ nano-forest. In general, an improvement of V_{OC} was observed over the time period of 50 days. Notably the devices were significantly stable due to the addition of cesium (triple cation), which is known to retards the back conversion of perovskites into PbI₂. V_{oc} was found to have negligible effect in both cases and improved PCE with time were obtained for TiO₂ nano-forest based photoanodes. Relatively stable solar cells were obtained with the presented photoanode prepared by PV-OAD technique due to its 1-directional orientation and slow recombination losses. The calculated drop in efficiency after 50 days was only 3.87% (from 17.169% to 16.50%) in case of 200nm, while for the standard one (mesoporous), the drop was about 13.35% (from 16.25% to 14.08%). This suggests that the infiltration of the perovskite in this NC-TiO₂ porous film is advantageous compared to the mesoporous TiO₂ layers with respect to the perovskite stability.

In order to explore the dynamical processes occurring in the devices under real operation conditions, we have employed electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to obtain information regarding recombination processes, carrier lifetime. In the past these techniques have been used to unravel electron dynamics first in DSSCs and lately in PSCs. In EIS, we probe the system response on the application of a sinusoidal signal, e.g.: $E = E_0 \sin(\omega t)$, where E_0 is the signal amplitude, $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency, and f is the signal frequency. This signal is of the order of a few mV, therefore the response can be linearized so that specific frequencies characteristic of the device can be detected³¹.

Figure 7. Recombination resistance as obtained from fittings to an $-R(R_{rec}C)$ - equivalent circuit of the impedance response of all studied devices.

In figure 7, recombination resistance is shown versus voltage. An equivalent circuit (figure 8a) was used to obtain the recombination resistance and capacitance of the devices. However, it was reported³²⁻³⁴ that capacitance in the perovskite is typically controlled by the geometrical component, which it can be expressed by the expression, $C_g = \epsilon \epsilon_0 A/d$, where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the perovskite, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, A the effective contact area and d the thickness. R_{rec} is expected to decrease exponentially with voltage, meanwhile that capacitance extracted from the high frequency component is indeed constant respect with applied voltage as expected from a geometrical nature. This is well corroborated in our study as it can be seen in

figure 7 and S1 respectively. Additionally, it can be extracted that nano-forest structure possess higher recombination resistance than mesoporous TiO₂, which it could be attributed to a better interconnection between perovskite and electron transport layer, unidirectional flow of charges, therefore a better carrier extraction.

Time constants for the lifetime of the carriers can be acquired from EIS. Figure S2 shows the complex plane plot of a PSC with different TiO₂ as selective contacts. Theoretically, depending on the time constants (semicircles) appeared in the plot, cumbersome the analysis becomes. Nevertheless, the peak appearing at larger frequencies is associated to the recombination of carriers³⁵. In this aspects, from EIS results, a time constant can be estimated by means of two different formulas. First, from the inverse of the maximum angular frequency but it can also be expressed in terms of recombination resistance and capacitance:

Figure 8. a) Equivalent circuit used to analyze impedance measurements, b) time constant extracted from the maximum angular frequency and c) time constant from the recombination resistance and capacitance.

Figure 9. Electron lifetime versus voltage obtained by two different methods. FC= fit circle of the semicircle (w) and RC=recombination resistance and capacitance.

Electron lifetime follows also the same trend as recombination resistance (Fig. 9), which decays exponentially with voltage. When we plot (Fig. 10) the capacitance as a function of the frequency,

the trend shows the typical behavior of a PSC, showing a plateau at mid-frequency region, associated to the bulk capacitance of the perovskite³⁶⁻³⁸. It is well known the existence of different of charge carriers inside the hybrid perovskite solar cell. For instance, recent studies indicate that ionic movements inside the perovskite are identified at low-frequency ranges. In addition, there is an electrode polarization caused by an ion interfacial accumulation, which is the possible explanation of hysteresis behavior due to the perovskite layer's excess capacitance. Previous studies indicates the role of capacitance values at low-frequencies which would indicate the presence of higher hysteresis^{36,38-42}. This effect is in accordance with the results obtained in our study (figure S3 and Table S1) of different TiO₂ structures. It is observed how nano-forest of 200 nm presents lower slope values of capacitance at low-frequency and also lower values of HI. By using transient photovoltage analysis longer charge recombination lifetime was reported for 1-directional photoanode w.r.t to randomly packed 3-dimensional TiO₂ scaffold.¹³

Figure 10. Capacitance spectra depending on the TiO₂ structure contact measured at the same voltage.

Conclusions

A facile and industrially scalable method is reported for the deposition of 1-dimensional TiO₂ nano-forest. This was then used as photoanodes in perovskite solar cells. Porous and homogeneous 1D-TiO₂ thin films were fabricated through this proven methodology. The prepared photoanodes were then employed for perovskites solar cells fabrication and power conversion

efficiencies c.a.17% were obtained, which is so far the highest for 1-dimensional nanostructures ever reported. This performance proves that the presented methodology can meet the standards required for practical application and large area integration.

To summarize vertically aligned, ordered and transparent 1-D TiO₂ films were fabricated and employed as the photoanode. Photocurrent density as high as of 22.6 mA cm⁻² and an encouraging photovoltaic performance of 15% for mixed and 17% for triple cation based perovskites under standard full sun illumination were obtained. To the best of our knowledge, this is the highest reported power conversion efficiency reported for any nanostructures. Structural, morphological, and spectroscopic studies suggest that the TiO₂ structure influences the growth and dimensions of depositing perovskites. In spite of having relatively low loading of perovskites 1-D structures, improved photovoltaic performance were obtained, pointing towards more efficient charge collection/extraction as studied by the impedance spectroscopy. Furthermore, ageing tests carried out on unsealed devices suggests improved stability compare to 3-dimensional mesoporous structure. The facile electron collection in these 1-dimensional nano-forest devices resulted in more stable systems than those mesoporous ones prepared by spin coating TiO₂. We believe that the presented thin film process techniques brings new dimension for perovskite solar cells fabrication and facilitate easy integration.

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1-dimensional homogenous nanocolumnar structures prepared without any template method, for efficient perovskite solar cells fabrication.

